

Circular Array for Satcom Interference Rejection

Randall Musselman, Daniel Parker, John Hadjis, Derek Francis, Jordan Wind, and Nathan Walker

Department of Electrical Engineering
US Air Force Academy
Colorado Springs, CO USA

Abstract— A useful application of antenna arrays is interference rejection. This paper describes a circular antenna array that was designed to reject interference in a mobile satellite receiver from a close-proximity source of interference. Since this interference source can move relative to the satellite antenna, the antenna array must adaptively adjust its null direction accordingly. The particular design of the circular array necessitated a significant size reduction in the radiating elements. Therefore, size reduction techniques were applied to circular patch antennas to allow them to fit in the circular array.

Keywords—phased array; patch antenna; interference

I. INTRODUCTION

Electromagnetic interference can disrupt mobile satellite communication, especially when a high-power terrestrial interfering source is in close proximity to a mobile satellite receiver. Often these jamming sources are broadband and present significantly more power density on the receive antenna than the desired satellite signal, simply due to their close proximity relative to the transmitting satellite. In this case, the co-channel interference can easily overpower the desired satellite signal. In addition, adjacent-channel interference can also occur from these close-proximity interferers, due to non-ideal filtering. One way to mitigate this co-channel and adjacent-channel interference is with adaptive beam-forming phased-array antennas.

II. ARRAY DESIGN

Two general methods of adaptive beam steering could be considered for interference rejection, both of which would result in a favorable signal-to-interference ratio (SIR). The first method is to simply steer a narrow main beam toward the desired source, and presuming that the interfering signal is outside the narrow main beam, the satellite receiver would likely experience a useable SIR. While this main-beam steering method is theoretically possible, it is impractical for UHF frequencies, due to the required physical array size [1].

A more reasonable approach is to use an electrically smaller array without much directivity, and instead, rely on beam forming to create a deep null in the direction of the interference signal. Much less directivity is required to create a null than to create a narrow beam [1][2]. So without the need for high gain, the aperture size can be made much smaller. In fact, we were able to achieve a 20-dB steerable null with a

phased ring array, with only a 0.4-wavelength diameter, as shown in Fig. 1. At a frequency of 500MHz, the array diameter is only 0.24 meters in free space. The array factor for this equally-excited six-element array is [3]

$$f(\theta) = \sum_{n=1}^6 e^{j\{(\pi/2)\sin\theta\cos[\phi-2\pi(n/6)]+\alpha_n\}} \quad (1)$$

where

$$\alpha_n = -(\pi/2)\cos[\phi_o - 2\pi(n/6)] \quad (2)$$

is the required phase shift for each n th element, when the main beam is steered toward the horizon, i.e., $\theta_o = 90^\circ$, and toward the azimuth angle, ϕ_o . The null will be directed opposite the main beam, or $\phi_o \pm \pi$. This configuration allows us to steer in azimuth, (ϕ_o) as well as in elevation, (θ_o). However, in our application the terrestrial mobile receiver and interference transmitter will always be along the horizon, and the desired satellite signal will be elevated above the horizon. Therefore, we aim our main beam toward the horizon ($\theta_o = 90^\circ$), which in turn creates a null 180 degrees behind the main beam, also along the horizon. Since the array size is intentionally insufficient for high gain, there will be sufficient coverage at high elevation angles, even to the zenith ($\theta_o = 0^\circ$). This offers the advantage of only having to steer the three-dimensional antenna pattern in only two dimensions, i.e., azimuth only.

III. PATCH ELEMENT DESIGN

To further suppress interfering power from all compass angles (azimuth) along the horizon, we used circular patch antennas as the radiating elements, due to their three-dimensional antenna patterns, as well as their polarization versatility. However, patch antennas typically resonate with

Fig. 1. Six-element circular phased-array antenna, with circular patch elements.

dimensions that are one-half wavelength [3]. In free space, the six 0.5λ patches would overlap each other, as indicated by the size relationship shown in Fig. 2. So clearly a significant size reduction of the radiating elements is necessary. A diagram of the antenna array relating the array radius, r , with the patch radius, a , and the spacing between patches, s is shown in Fig. 3. The equilateral triangle formed by two of the six elements results in the relationship

$$a = \frac{r - s}{2}. \quad (3)$$

Since a gap between elements is necessary, the elements must be reduced by more than 50%, in order to prevent them from overlapping each other and to avoid mutual coupling. Fortunately, some size reduction is due to the dielectric constant of the material between the patch element and the ground plane [4]. We decided not to use exotic material, or even Roger’s Duroid with high permittivity, due to cost, ease of workability, and the decreased bandwidth that comes with higher dielectric constant. Therefore, we settled on readily available and inexpensive FR4 as our patch antenna material. This limited the dielectric constant to $\epsilon_r = 4.8$, which would ideally reduce the size by 45%. However, the effective relative permittivity is significantly less than the dielectric constant and depends on the substrate thickness, as well as the element radius. Therefore, we needed additional techniques to significantly reduce the patch size. Experimental results showed that an inter-element spacing of at least 7% of a wavelength provided a S_{21} scattering parameter between elements of at least 20dB. This spacing requirement resulted in a necessary size reduction of 75%, i.e., the actual patch could not exceed 25% of its resonant size in free space. There has been past effort to take advantage of the recursive nature of fractal antennas [1][5]; however, we seemed to acquire better results using slits in the radiating elements, which are known to make the radiating elements appear electrically larger, as well as increasing their bandwidth [6]. Fig. 4 shows a mask of the radiating patch element, which achieved the desired size reduction.

Fig. 2. Size comparison of the 0.2λ -diameter array (ring) and the 0.5λ -diameter radiating patch (solid) in free space.

Fig. 3. Size considerations for the six-element array of circular patch antennas.

The slits etched into the circular patches provided an additional 53% size reduction compared to the FR4 without the slits. The S_{11} scattering parameter for each of the modified patches, in Fig. 4, was measured, and a typical plot is shown in Fig. 5, indicating better than -15dB, which translates to an SWR of 1.4:1.

Fig. 4. Mask of radiating patch element. Diameter: 0.134λ ; slit lengths: 0.127λ and 0.067λ ; and slit width: 0.004λ . Feed probes were placed 0.045λ from the outer edge.

Fig. 5. Measured S_{11} of the circular patch antenna shown above.

Fig. 6. Radiation pattern of a single patch element.

The radiation pattern of a single element is shown in Fig. 6 and illustrates that the element pattern itself provides at least 6dB of attenuation in the horizontal direction, compared to the zenith, even before applying the array factor. Since the actual radiation pattern is the product of the element and array factors, this 6dB of suppression along the horizon will add to the attenuation of the null that the array creates.

IV. BEAMFORMING

Equation (2) was programmed for azimuth angles in 10-degree increments, in order to generate the required phase shifts for each element to combine and form the pattern described by (1). Fig. 7 shows typical measured azimuth patterns for two particular steered azimuth angles, each toward the horizon. These patterns indicate that the depth of the null in the horizontal plane is typically 20dB, compared to the maximum power in the horizontal plane. Fig. 8 is an elevation pattern in the vertical plane that is perpendicular to the plane containing

the null. This elevation pattern indicates that there is 10dB of attenuation from zenith to horizon that will add to the attenuation created by the null, not shown in Fig. 8. Combining the attenuation from the elevation and azimuth patterns, along the horizontal plane, the steerable null provides more than 30dB of attenuation relative to the zenith direction.

V. INTERFERENCE TRACKING

Two identical beam-forming networks were connected to the array, each consisting of amplifiers, programmable phase shifters, and combiners, which formed antenna patterns similar to Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. One of these networks acted as a scanner, continuously rotating the null in azimuth, while an on-board computer controlled phase shifter and recorded the received power level. The system kept track of the direction of the least power received, and directed the other identical beam-forming network to lock its null toward that direction. This locked-on beam-former was connected to the receiver. As the interference signal changed directions with respect to the array, the system immediately tracked the new angle and updated the required phases in order to steer the null of the second beam-former in that direction, thus maintaining the antenna-pattern null in the direction of the interference signal. Our application allowed for this simple tracking routine because if the particular interference signal of concern was present, it always overpowered the satellite signal in the horizontal direction. When the offending transmitter was sufficiently far so that this assumption was invalid, it no longer created an interference problem, and the phases were adjusted to turn off the null, creating an omnidirectional pattern. For a more general application, when the desired signal cannot be assumed to emit from above the horizon, this simple approach would prove insufficient. However, there are numerous adaptive-null steering techniques that rely on more exotic algorithms that can be combined with this array[8].

Fig. 7. Measured azimuth (horizontal) patterns, indicating 20dB of suppression in the null.

Fig. 7. Elevation pattern of the six-element phased array, showing 10dB zenith/horizon ratio.

VI. TESTING

As a proof of functionality, the circular array, along with controlling circuitry and the two beam-forming networks, was tested in an anechoic chamber. The system successfully suppressed an interference signal from a 20-Watt transmitter, through a 7dB antenna that was only three feet from the array, while simultaneously receiving a signal from a much weaker 300mW transmitter, through a 0dB antenna that was 25 feet from the array. This transmit-power and distance difference represents a -20dB SIR, which the array was able to resolve to a full-quieting signal through a receiver that was connected to the array. The test setup is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Test setup in anechoic chamber, interference antenna in foreground; array under test in background.

VII. CONCLUSION

A six-element phased array, in a ring configuration, of circular patch antennas was constructed, resulting in radiation patterns that created a steerable 20dB null in azimuth. Combined with the 10dB of attenuation at the horizon, compared to the zenith, 30dB of attenuation could be steered in all 360-degrees of azimuth to suppress interference in a satellite communication receiver. This system was used to successfully locate an interference signal and to produce a full-quieting radio signal in the presence of a -20dB signal to interference ratio.

REFERENCES

- [1] Randall Musselman, Shawn Killpack, Brett Killion, Eric Herbort, Paul Kim, and Ron Todd, "Broadband-Interference Rejection for Mobile Satellite Communications", *Proceedings of 2010 IEEE International Conference on Wireless Information Technology and Systems*, Honolulu, September 2010.
- [2] Randall Musselman, Shawn Killpack, Brett Killion, Eric Herbort, Paul Kim, and Ron Todd, "Adaptive Null-Steered Interference-Rejection for a Mobile Satellite Receiver", *Proceedings of 2010 IEEE International Symposium on Phased Array Systems & Technology*, Boston, October 2010.
- [3] Constantine A. Balanis, *Antenna Theory Analysis and Design*, New York, Harper & Row, 1982.
- [4] Warren L. Stutzman, "Estimating Directivity and Gain of Antennas" *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Magazine*, Vol. 40, No. 4, August 1998.
- [5] Warren L. Stutzman and Gary A. Thiele, *Antenna Theory and Design*, 2nd Ed., New York, John Wiley & Sons, 1998.
- [6] Douglas H. Werner, Randy L. Haupt, and Pingjuan L. Werner, "Fractal Antenna Engineering: The Theory and Design of Fractal Antenna Arrays", *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Magazine*, Vol. 41, No. 5, October 1999.
- [7] Kin-Lu Wong, *Compact and Broadband Microstrip Antennas*, New York, John Wiley & Sons, 2002.